

SuHAMK CoARAb Project: List of Qualitative Researcher Evaluation Criteria (Draft 1)

Evaluation Criteria	Description	Qualitative Measures	
<p>Academic Research</p>	<p>Published publications</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variation in role • Variation of collaborations • Variation of sole authorship and multi authorship • Continued activeness in publishing • Researchers perceived 'most important' contributions • The extent of open access to produced research • Use of specialization and interdisciplinary • Application of regional, national, international strategies • Suitability with HAMK strategy or education units • On which platforms has the research been disseminated 	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The extent of ‘open access’ being utilized • Ethics, reliability and replicability of research • The extent of inclusion or consideration of students, teachers or study units 	
<p>Practical research</p>	<p>Produced knowledge, products, services, etc. for stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variation of role in practical research • The extent of stakeholder inclusion in research, project, service development etc. • Proclaimed stakeholder benefit • Continued activeness in practical research • Researchers perceived ‘most important’ contributions • Practical adoption of research, knowledge, service etc. by stakeholders • Interdisciplinary approach (use of multiple researchers, disciplines, partners etc). 	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application or consideration of regional, national or international strategies • Suitability with HAMK strategy or education units • On which platforms has the research been disseminated • The extent of 'open access' being utilized • Ethics, reliability and replicability of research • The extent of inclusion or consideration of students, teachers or study units 	
Funding applications	Inclusion of both successful and unsuccessful funding applications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variation of role in funding applications • Variation of applied to funding sources • Variation in type of funding applied to • Quality of funding applications • Variation of partner, SH and discipline collaboration 	

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Results Dissemination	Communication of research, projects, research results and project results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variation of communication platforms used • Variation of languages used • Variation of target audiences • The research or research results are presented in a manner suitable for the audience • Extent of open access of research and research results • Utilization of research or results by students, teachers or study units, 	
Soft Communication Skills	UAS researcher interpersonal communication skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variation in stakeholder interaction 	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variation of stakeholder collaboration • Variation of face-to-face communication experience • Variation of partner collaborations • Variation of team collaborations • Successful and effective stakeholder, team and partner collaboration • Variation of educational communication experience • Variation of collaboration with teachers and/or students 	
<p>Non-verbal Communication Skills</p>	<p>Non-verbal communication skills, including different writing skills, creation of presentations, educational materials, diagrams etc.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variation of communication channels and platforms used • Variation in mediums used to present research and data • Role in writing and/or editing funding applications • Role in writing and/or editing publications 	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation of marketing and pitching material • Preparation of presentation material • Preparation of teaching material • Variation of target audiences 	
Teamwork and Collaboration Skills	Experience in teamwork and collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variation of authorship collaborations • Variation of project collaborations • Variations of study unit or student collaborations • Variation of partner collaborations • Variation of interdisciplinary collaborations • Variation of stakeholder collaborations • Proclaimed successful and effective collaboration 	
Field Expertise	Practical and academic understanding of own field	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peer recognition • Continued activeness in field networks • Continued activeness in field events 	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical experience of field • Belongs to field networks • Continued activeness in field relevant authorship • Continued activeness in field relevant projects • Continued activeness in field relevant funding applications • Active in relevant dialogues, debates and discussions • Recognised specialist role in workshops, presentations, lectures, employment 	
Self-Reflective Skills	Proactive in career development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognition of own strengths and weaknesses • Activeness in educational courses • Activeness in career development courses 	
Leadership Skills	Skills needed for leading research and project teams	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experience in leadership roles • Variation in roles including leadership roles 	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experience in leading research teams • Experience in leading project teams • Participation in leadership courses • Experience in providing peer feedback • Demonstrates leadership values similar to organisation • Successful and effective leadership accomplishment 	
Mentoring and Supervision Skills	Skills needed for supervision and mentoring duties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experience in supervision roles • Experience in providing peer feedback • Demonstrates mentoring values similar to organisation • Experience in mentoring roles • Successful and effective supervision or mentoring accomplishment 	
Networking skills		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activeness in field events and activities 	

	<p>Skills needed for networking and potential for existing networks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variation of collaborations • Existing networks • Existing contacts in field with network potential • Experience in networking roles • peer recognition 	
<p>Pedagogical skills</p>	<p>Skills needed for education and teaching</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experience in teaching roles • Production of teaching materials • Successful and effective teaching accomplishments • Completion of teaching courses • Variation in teaching roles • Utilization of teachers and/or students in research or projects • Dissemination of research or projects in to education • Research or projects utilized in study units 	

The parts **highlighted in yellow** in the above table are criteria which need to be further considered. They have been highlighted as criteria which may be difficult to evaluate especially in the recruitment phase. Their current inclusion as official qualitative researcher evaluation criteria is still under consideration.